

**Strainless Monocyclic Rings. Part I. Isomerism of
4-Methylcyclohexane-1-carboxy-1-acetic Acid.
Some Evidences of Strainless *cyclo*Hexane
Ring.**

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From a consideration of the closed carbon rings on the model it is evident that in the case of three, four and five membered rings the carbon tetrahedra are incapable of free rotation round their valency bonds, these rings will thus be co-planar and consequently more or less strained ones, whereas in six and higher membered rings this rotation is possible ; and then the planar and highly strained structures for these rings may no longer exist, the strained form passing into the strainless multiplanar configuration. For a *cyclohexane* ring this spatial structure free from strain has been found by Mohr (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1918, **98**, 315) and Sachse (*Ber.*, 1890, **23**, 1363) to be capable of existing in two modifications represented by a boat and a chair-shaped configuration.

According to the modern conceptions, the molecules of any substance are dynamic *i.e.*, they are moving incessantly. Mohr (*loc. cit.*) concluded from an examination of the models that the strain involved in the interconversion of Sachse's strainless forms of *cyclohexane* ring is so slight that it is overcome by this inter-molecular collision which brings about the intra-molecular rotation in the carbon atoms of the rings and hence, although theoretically possible, the two forms of *cyclohexane* itself have not yet been isolated, one being easily converted into the other. The passage of one into the other form, however, will necessitate an intermediate structure which is planar and consequently a strained one.

This will be the state of affairs unless at least two of the carbon atoms in the ring are substituted which may bring about a sort of check to the free rotatory motion of the atoms inside the molecule, resulting in the total arrest or a tendency towards arrest of the intra-molecular motion stabilising it in one or the other isomeric modifications of the same compound, which may then be capable of being isolated. The case of dcahydronaphthalene can be taken as a specific illustration of this hypothesis; here, the taking part of two carbon atoms of one six-membered ring in the formation of an

adjacent six-carbon structure causes a complete arrest of the intramolecular rotatory motion of all the carbon atoms round their valency bonds, rendering the molecule static so far as the internal motion is concerned. Justification of the hypothesis has been very adequately supplied by the observations of Hückel and his collaborators (Hückel, *Annalen*, 1925, **441**, 1 ; 1927, **415**, 109; Hückel and Friedrich, *ibid*, 1926, **451**, 132 ; Hückel and Stepf, *ibid*, 1927, **453**, 163), who very successfully isolated the various isomeric derivatives of decahydronaphthalene as necessitated by the theory. While discussing the *cyclohexane* ring in particular, it should be mentioned here that either in *cyclohexane* molecule itself or in any monosubstituted *cyclohexane* compound, the factor which arrests the free rotational motion of the carbon tetrahedra is either absent or is only very feeble. Also it should be mentioned that the energy required to overcome the resistance in the interconversion of the two strainless forms in *cyclohexane* is only very slight; the consequence is that up till now no evidence of the strainless *cyclohexane* ring has been obtained. Several workers have investigated into the matter but apparently without success. Unfortunately in their investigations they did not take notice of this particular factor which alone can stabilise the different stereoisomeric forms (compare *e.g.* Wightmann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, p. 2541). Chavanne and Becker (*Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1922, **31**, 95) carried out some experiments on the reduction of the three xylenes and particularly in the case of the *ortho* compound they observed that different products were obtained by using nickel and platinum as catalysts in the hydrogenation processes. The isomerism may be of the ordinary kind, which is explicable on the assumption of a planar structure for the *cyclohexane* ring and which is caused by the different positions of methyl groups and hydrogen atoms with respect to the plane of the ring, just as has been observed to be the case with hexahydro-*p*-toluic acid (I) (Einhorn and Willstätter, *Annalen*, 1894, **280**, 160) or it might be due to the existence of multiplanar configuration of the *cyclohexane* ring, when not only these but two more stereoisomers will be capable of existence. It has not been definitely settled, however, whether the isomerism of these hydrogenated xylenes is of the former or latter type. The separation and characterisation of these dimethyl*cyclohexanes* does apparently involve a good deal of difficulty. In order to establish definitely the truth of the hypothesis in question, attention has now been directed towards the synthesis and separation of

some other derivatives of *cyclohexane*, in which at least two of the carbon atoms are more or less heavily substituted, so that the molecular volume of the substituents exert influences which may be effective enough in stabilising the strainless configurations and render it possible to isolate the different isomeric derivatives as necessitated by the hypothesis.

If, by virtue of the heavy substituents, the *cyclohexane* molecule is rendered static in the puckered forms, then only, on consideration of models, it will be found that a compound of the type 'II) should exist in four stereoisomeric modifications (Figs. I, II, III and IV respectively), two of them will have the boat (Figs. I and II) and the other two the chair-shaped (Figs. III and IV) configurations. If we were to term the former pair *cis* and the latter *trans*-structures then again the *cis* compound will have either a *cis-cis* or *cis-trans* configuration according as the substituents R and X lie on the same or opposite directions of the plane occupied by the four carbon atoms marked with asterisk and lying in a plane perpendicular to it. Similarly the second set of compounds would be called *trans-cis* and *trans-trans* isomers with respect to the position occupied by the substituents R, X, R' and Y.

In these compounds by virtue of the molecular volumes of the substituents R, R', X and Y, as discussed above, there will be a tendency to prevent the internal motion of the molecule and make it possible to isolate all the four stereoisomers which might or might not be convertible into one another, according as the molecular volumes of the substituents are bulky enough to arrest the intramolecular motion completely or not.

An acid (V) corresponding to the type (II) has now been prepared and it has been possible to isolate all the four probable isomers of the same. As at present we have no means to classify them and definitely assign a *cis-cis* or a *cis-trans* structure to one or the other of these compounds they have provisionally been named as acids A, B, C and D respectively.

4-Methylcyclohexanone condenses well in presence of piperidine with ethyl cyanoacetate, yielding the unsaturated cyano-ester (III). This ester, when condensed with potassium cyanide according to the method of Lapworth and McRae (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2741) in alcoholic solution, yields the dicyano-ester (IV), which on hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid gives a mixture of the isomeric acids of the constitution (V), a compound which is similar to that represented by the formula (II), where R=Me, R'=H, X=CH₂.CO₂H and Y=CO₂H.

The process of separation of these acids is a tedious and difficult one, but when the details enumerated in the experimental portion are strictly adhered to, they can be obtained in four distinct modifica-

tions. All these acids yield anhydrides (VI), which should also exist in four stereoisomeric forms, for which multiplanar structures according to the configurations of the acids can be assigned. In fact, all these anhydrides have been isolated of which three are solids melting respectively at 77°, 59° and 104° while the fourth is a liquid under ordinary conditions. From each of these acids different anilic acids (VII) have been obtained melting at 195°, 185°, 183° and 184° respectively and from three of these different anils (VIII) have also been prepared. The acids themselves, however, melt respectively at 137°, 129°, 174° and 146°.

There was just a possibility that some of these acids might have been derived from the other isomeric methylcyclohexanones which might have been present along with the *para*-ketone used, as impurity. To eliminate this possibility, the acids (IX) and (X) have also been synthesised from the corresponding ketones, and the acids so far obtained do not appear to be similar to any of these four acids. A description of these, however, is reserved for a future communication.

It is doubtful whether the conditions for stabilising the strainless forms in the acid (I) and other similar acids such as *p*-methylcyclohexaneacetic acid (XI) (Wallach and Evans, *Annalen*, 1907, 353, 313; Perkin and Pope, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1075) are fully present in them. Like hexahydrophthalic acid (XII) (Baeyer, *Annalen*, 1890, 258, 218) these acids have so far been found to occur in not

more than two stereoisomeric forms; a detailed and more searching examination has already been undertaken with these acids along with a series of similar compounds of different types and the results will be communicated in due course.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl *p*-methylcyclohexylidenecyanoacetate was prepared with slight modification of the method of Hardinge, Haworth and Perkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1958) thus: *p*-Methylcyclohexanone (224 g.) and ethyl cyanoacetate (226 g.) were mixed together and to the mixture 4 c.c. of piperidine were added, when the mixture became warm and globules of water began to separate. This was left for 40 hours at the ordinary temperature and then heated on the steam-bath for two hours. To the mixture was then added excess of water and the solution acidified with hydrochloric acid and the oil that was precipitated was taken up in ether, washed and dried over calcium chloride and then fractionated in a vacuum. At first some unchanged ketone and cyano-ester come over and then the unsaturated ester distils at 166°/13 mm. The unchanged mixture of ketone and cyano-ester was treated again with 3 c.c. of piperidine and worked up as described above, when some more of the same unsaturated cyano-ester was obtained (total yield 80%).

When re-distilled the ester had b. p. 165°/12 mm.; $d_4^{16.4} = 1.02877$, $n_D^{16.4} = 1.49118$ whence $[R_L]_D = 58.29$ (calc. 56.36). The exaltation is due to the presence of a conjugated system.

Ethyl 4-Methylcyclohexane-1-cyano-1-α-cyanoacetate.—The addition of potassium cyanide to the unsaturated cyano-ester (III) was effected according to the method of Lapworth and McRae (*loc. cit.*) with some modifications, mainly on the line of those adopted by Bardhan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, p. 2591) which briefly is as follows. The unsaturated ester (100 g.) was dissolved in rectified spirit (430 c.c.) and to this was added a solution of potassium cyanide (54 g.) in water (135 c.c.). The solution became hot soon after the addition of potassium cyanide and after 24 hours scaly shining crystal of

the potassium salt of the addition compound began to separate. This was left to stand for 8 days in order to allow the reaction to be complete. The alcohol was then removed on the water-bath and finally under reduced pressure. The coloured residue of the salt of the dicyano-ester was then hydrolysed without being isolated.

Hydrolysis of the Dicyano-ester (IV): Preparation of the Mixture of the Succinic Acids.—The dark coloured residue obtained in the previous experiment was hydrolysed with 700 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid by heating for 8-9 hours with a reflux condenser. The solution was then cooled, diluted and extracted with ether. The acid was removed from the ethereal extract by washing with a solution of sodium carbonate. The ethereal solution gave some solid neutral product which could be crystallised from hot water or dilute alcohol when it melted indefinitely at 139-44° and appeared to be mixture of the imides of the succinic acids.

The alkaline solution on being acidified with dry hydrochloric acid precipitated an acid which was taken up in ether, dried and the solvent removed, when it was obtained as a solid of indefinite melting point. The yield of the acid is 50 g.

Separation of the Acids.—The crude mixture of acids was neutralised with a solution of ammonia and the clear solution was evaporated on the water-bath to dryness. The dry ammonium salt was then extracted with enough hot absolute alcohol and filtered off. The solid on the filter funnel was washed several times with small quantities of the hot solvent. The solid thus obtained was dried in the air and then treated with water, when excepting a negligibly small residue the whole of it dissolved. The clear filtered solution was acidified and extracted with ether. The dried ethereal extract left a solid which did not appear to be quite pure neither could purification of it be effected by fractional crystallisation. The whole of the acid was, therefore, refluxed for two hours with a slight excess of acetic anhydride and the product was fractionated in a vacuum. On removing the acetic acid and the excess of acetic anhydride, the anhydride of the succinic acid was obtained which distilled at 154°/12 mm. and set to a hard crystalline mass in the receiver. The crude anhydride melted indefinitely at 55-60°. This was then crystallised from petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) when two kinds of crystals were obtained. Those that separated at first are hard and heavy rhombic cubes. At a certain stage the crystallisation of this fraction is almost complete. If care is taken to watch the

solution at this stage, the supernatant liquid can be decanted off at this point and these crystals can then be purified by one more crystallisation from the same solvent. Or else, if only one crystal of the second anhydride separates out, the whole of it is thrown out of solution in rapid succession. This second anhydride is in appearance purely white flakes and is very light. It is, therefore, possible to separate them mechanically by shaking with cold petroleum and decanting the solution, when the first formed heavy crystals sink to the bottom and usually do not come along with these. By careful manipulation, however the two can thus be obtained as distinct solid bodies, which are quite pure after two or three crystallisations.

The Acid A.—The first of these anhydrides, say the anhydride of the acid (A), melts at 77° . (Found: C, 66.0; H, 7.9. $C_{10}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 65.9; H, 7.7 per cent.).

The acid (A) itself was obtained from this anhydride by hydrolysing it with dilute caustic soda solution. It crystallises well from benzene and melts at 137° . (Found: C, 60.0; H, 8.0; M. W. by titration, 200. $C_{10}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 60.0; H, 8.0 per cent. M. W., 200).

The *anilic acid* was obtained by adding a solution of aniline (1 mol.) in benzene to a benzene solution of the anhydride, m. p. 77° (1 mol.). After a few minutes some crystalline solid separated which dissolved completely in a solution of dilute sodium carbonate. The alkaline solution on acidification gave the free anilic acid, which crystallises from dilute alcohol in long prismatic needles and melts at 195° . (Found: C, 70.0; H, 7.8. $C_{16}H_{21}O_3N$ requires C, 69.8; H, 7.6 per cent.).

The *anil* was prepared by heating this anilic acid at $200-10^{\circ}$ for about 15 minutes. The melt was cooled, washed with a solution of sodium carbonate and water and then crystallised from alcohol when it separated in short needles, m. p. 130° . (Found: C, 74.4; H, 7.4. $C_{16}H_{19}O_2N$ requires C, 74.7; H, 7.4 per cent.).

The *imide* was obtained by heating the dry ammonium salt of the acid (A), in a test tube for some time on a very small flame. When the decomposition was complete, which took about 20 minutes to half an hour, the melt was cooled and the solid thus obtained was washed with water, dilute sodium carbonate solution and again water and was crystallised from dilute alcohol, when it

came out in thin lustrous laminae, m. p. 119.20° . (Found: C, 66.6 ; H, 8.2. $C_{10}H_{15}O_3N$ requires C, 66.3 ; H, 8.3 per cent.)

p-Toluidinamic acid was precipitated when solutions of the anhydride and *p*-toluidine in benzene were mixed together in molecular proportion. The solid which is completely soluble in a solution of sodium carbonate, was purified by crystallisation from dilute alcohol, when it melted at 199° . (Found: C, 71.0 ; H, 7.8. $C_{17}H_{23}O_3N$ requires C, 70.6 ; H, 7.9 per cent.)

p-Toluidinimide was prepared by heating the above *p*-toluidinamic acid at about $210-15^{\circ}$. When the decomposition was complete, the melt was cooled, washed with a solution of dilute sodium carbonate and water and then crystallised from alcohol, when it melts at 119° . (Found: C, 75.7 ; H, 7.8. $C_{17}H_{21}O_2N$ requires C, 75.3 ; H, 7.8 per cent.)

β -Naphthylamic Acid was obtained from the corresponding anhydride in a way similar to the other amic acids. It crystallises from dilute alcohol and melts at 200° . (Found: C, 74.2 ; H, 6.9. $C_{20}H_{23}O_3N$ requires C, 73.8 ; H, 7.0 per cent.)

β -Naphthylimide was obtained from the corresponding naphthylamic acid in the usual way. It crystallises from dilute alcohol and melts at 162° . (Found: C, 78.8 ; H, 6.7. $C_{20}H_{21}O_2N$ requires C, 78.4 ; H, 6.8 per cent.)

The Acid (B).—As mentioned above the second anhydride, *i.e.*, the anhydride of the acid (B), was obtained from the petroleum mother-liquor of the anhydride of the acid (A), m. p. 77° . This was re-crystallised from the same solvent when it was obtained in thin lustrous laminae and melted at 59° . (Found: C, 65.7 ; H, 7.7 per cent.)

The *acid* (B) itself was obtained from the anhydride (m. p. 59°) by alkaline hydrolysis and was crystallised from benzene, from which it separated in prismatic needles, m. p. 129° . (Found: C, 60.0 ; H, 7.8 per cent. M. W. by titration, 200.)

The corresponding *anilic acid* was prepared in a way similar to that in the previous case. It crystallises from the same solvent and melts at 183° . (Found: C, 70.0 ; H, 7.5 per cent.)

The *anil* obtained by the usual method crystallised from alcohol and melted at $142-43^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 74.6 ; H, 7.5 per cent.)

The *imide* was isolated as the product of decomposition of the dry ammonium salt of the pure acid obtained from the anhydride, m. p. 59° . It crystallises in beautiful needles from hot water or

better from very dilute alcohol and melts at 130°. (Found: C, 66.7 ; H, 8.1 per cent.).

p-Toluidinamic acid resulted from the anhydride, m. p. 59°, and *p*-toluidine in the usual way. It crystallises from dilute alcohol and melts at 174°. (Found: C, 71.1 ; H, 7.9 per cent.).

p-Toluidinimide was obtained by the decomposition of the above *p*-toluidinamic acid a few degree above its melting point and crystallised from alcohol m. p. 134°. (Found: C, 75.7 ; H, 7.9 per cent.).

β-Naphthylamic acid prepared in the usual method crystallises from dilute alcohol and melts with decomposition at 192°. (Found: C, 74.2 ; H, 6.8 per cent.).

The corresponding *β-naphthylimide* crystallises from alcohol and melts at 144°. (Found: C, 78.7 ; H, 6.7 per cent.).

The Acids (C) and (D).—The alcoholic mother-liquor from the mixed ammonium salts was cooled when some crystalline solid was obtained. This was treated with water, which dissolved it partially and the insoluble substance appeared to be a neutral product containing nitrogen, this is probably an imide but is found to be different from those described above. On hydrolysis this imide gave an acid melting at 174° which is identical with the acid of the same melting point described below.

The cold alcoholic mother-liquor was now heated on the water-bath to remove the solvent and the small quantity of residue was preserved and after several experiments worked up as follows. The slightly pasty mass was treated with water and the traces of insoluble oily impurity removed by ether and the aqueous solution acidified and extracted with the same solvent. This latter ethereal solution left a semi-solid mass on removal of the solvent, which was extracted with hot benzene when some crystalline solid was left behind and the rest went into solution. The benzene solution was cooled with constant shaking and then filtered off. The solid which is practically insoluble in cold benzene was found to be an acid (*acid C*) isomeric with the two described above. It crystallises from acetic acid in stout prisms and melts at 174°. (Found: C, 60.0; H, 8.0 per cent. M. W. by titration, 200).

The *anhydride* of this acid was obtained by heating the acid (8 g.) with acetyl chloride (10 c.c.) on the water-bath for some time. Hydrogen chloride was given off and the acid went into solution. The excess of acetyl chloride and acetic acid was removed by evaporation on the water-bath and the residue was left

in an evacuated desiccator over caustic potash for a few days, when a solid anhydride was obtained. It crystallises in large shimmering plates from petroleum (b. p. 75-95°) and melts at 104°. (Found: C, 65·8 ; H, 7·6 per cent.).

The *anilic acid* prepared from this anhydride crystallises from alcohol and melts at 185°. (Found: C, 70·5 ; H, 7·8 per cent.).

The corresponding *anil* obtained in the usual way melts at the same temperature as the *anilic acid* itself namely 185° but it is insoluble in a solution of sodium carbonate while the other dissolves in it completely. (Found: C, 75·0 ; H, 7·2 per cent.).

The Acid (D).—From the benzene mother-liquor of the acid (C) the solvent was evaporated off on the water-bath and the residual gummy product was treated with petroleum (b. p. 75-95°) while the mass was still hot, when some crystalline solid separated out. This was treated with cold benzene which dissolved it practically completely leaving only traces of the acid (C). On the addition of petroleum to this cold benzene solution the fourth acid crystallises out after some time. This was re-crystallised from the same solvent and finally crystallised from hot water when it melted at 146°. (Found: C, 60·3 ; H, 7·8 per cent. M. W. by titration, 200).

The acid on being treated with acetyl chloride gave a liquid *anhydride*, which on being mixed with aniline gave an *anilic acid* melting at 184°. (Found: C, 70·5 ; H, 8·0 per cent.).

The petroleum mother-liquor from the fourth acid on removal of the solvent left a small amount of a viscous mass which has not yet been examined.

I desire to mention here that part of this work was done in the laboratory of Prof. J. F. Thrope, C.B.E., F.R.S., D.Sc., at the Imperial College of Science and Technology, South Kensington, London.

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